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The Housing Deprivation Rate in Europe

It decreased by 40% on average for the countries analyzed between 2010 and 2020

The Eurostat calculates the value of the housing deprivation rate in Europe. Housing deprivation is defined as the percentage of the population that lives in an overcrowded house. Housing deprivation is calculated considering the families who live in houses with a roof that loses, without bathroom or shower, without internal toilets, or in a not sufficiently illuminated house.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the housing deprivation rate in Europe in 2020. Turkey is in the first place for the value of the housing deprivation rate with an amount of 21.90%, followed by Romania with an amount of 14.30% and from Latvia with an amount of 11.50%. In the middle of the standings there are Slovenia with an amount of 3.10%, followed by Austria with an amount of 3.00% and by Denmark with an amount of 2.80%. The ranking Malta, Finland, and Norway close with an amount of 1.00%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of housing deprivation between 2010 and 2021. The Netherlands is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation between 2010 and 2021 with an amount of 200.00% equal to 1 unit, followed by Ireland with a value of 180.0 =% equal to 0.90 units and by Denmark with an amount of 115.38% equal to an amount of 1.50 units. In the middle of the standings there are Greece with an amount of -23.68% equal to an amount of -1.80 units, followed by Austria with a value of -25.00% equal to an amount of -1.00 units and from Turkey with an amount of -28.20% equal to an amount of -8.60 units. Lithuania closes the ranking with an amount of -60.00% equal to an amount of -8.10 units, followed by Slovenia with an amount of -79.87% equal to an amount of -12.30 units and from Estonia with an amount of -81.58% equal to an amount of -9.30 units. The serious housing deprivation decreased in the period considered on average from an amount of 7.48% up to a value of 4.5% or equal to an amount of -39.86% equal to -2.98 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The data show the presence of three different Clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Estonia, Portugal, Slovakia, Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Finland, Ireland, the Netherlands, Sweden, Belgium, Norway, Cyprus, Luxembourg, Switzerland, Spain, Malta, Germany,
- Cluster 2: Romania, Türkiye, Latvia, Hungary;
- Cluster 3: Croatia, Lithuania, Italy, Slovenia, Bulgaria, Greece.

From the point of view of the median, the following order is or $C2 = 12.0 > C3 = 5.6 > C1 = 2$. From a geographical point of view, it appears that housing deprivation is serious in the countries of South-East Europe and more sustainable in the countries of northern Europe.

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Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is created below with the Euclidean distance. Two structures are identified with complex networks. There is a network structure as indicated below or:

- Switzerland has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.14 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Switzerland for an amount of 0.14 units and with Germany for an amount of 0.097 units;
- Germany has a connection with Luxembourg equal to an amount of 0.097.

The following structures with complex networks are also detected or:

- Spain has a connection with Malta for an amount of 0.13 units;
- Malta has a connection with Spain to modernize 0.13 units, with Cyprus for an amount of 0.12 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.15 units;
- Cyprus has a connection with Malta for an amount of 0.12 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.12 units;
- Norway has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.12 units, with mortar for a value of 0.15 units, with Finland for an amount of 0.11 units and with Ireland for an amount of 0, 14 units;
- Ireland has a connection with Norway equal to an amount of 0.14 units, with Finland for an amount of 0.13 units, and with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.15 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with Ireland for an amount of 0.15 units and with Finland for an amount of 0.15 units;
- Finland has a connection with Ireland for an amount of 0.13 units, with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.15 units and with Norway equal to an amount of 0.11 units.

Obviously, these connections must not be considered as the cause-effect relationships. On the contrary, these are structures that highlight the presence of similar trends in the dynamics of the historical series of the countries considered united in the same network.

Conclusions. The value of housing deprivation decreased by about 40% between 2010 and 2021 on average in the countries considered. However, there are countries in which housing deprivation grew between 2010 and 2020, and among these the most relevant values were recorded in the Netherlands, Ireland and Denmark. However, if we consider the countries individually, it is possible to note that some countries have a real problem of housing deprivation. Among these certainly Turkey with about 21.90% of the population that lives housing deprivation. Italy also has a problem of housing deprivation with about 6.10% of the population, i.e. about 3.8 million people living in conditions of uncomfortable in accessing home good. However, it is likely that the increase in the price of the houses that occurred in connection of Covid-19 can worsen the condition of housing deprivation in the short term.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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References

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6516438>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Individuals with Risk Behaviors in the Consumption of Alcohol in Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636364>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrande. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Years of Life Lost for Exposure to PM2.5 in Europe. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799937>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). The Perception of Good Health in Europe. *International Web Post.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799948>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Healthy Life Expectancy in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799956>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Nitrate in Groundwater in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7799995>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Ammonia Emissions in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806877>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Use of Hazardous Pesticides in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806908>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Areas Cultivated with Organic Agriculture in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806941>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Public Expenditure for Research and Development in Agriculture in EU, USA, and Japan. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7806965>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). The Material and Social Deprivation in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811428>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Workers at Risk of Poverty in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811442>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). Turnover in the Service Sector in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811492>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). People Who Remain Poor Even After Social Transfers in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811683>

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). The Economic Sentiment Indicator in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811634>

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: a panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Angelo Leogrande. (2023). People Who Live in Families With Low Work Intensity in Europe. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7811718>

Appendix

C2>C3>C1

- C1
- C2
- C3

